

Will a Native Centered Education Reduce Unnecessary Placement in Special Education?

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>The Common Core State Standards are the most common policies set in place focused on grades kindergarten to twelfth grade Mathematics and Language Arts/Literacy. Students who do not meet these set standards may be falling behind in academic achievement or worse misplaced and mis-categorized when they're in need of specialized programs. It has been recently changed in some schools and districts to provide alternative teaching strategies including use of cultural and linguistic sensitivity. However, these new strategies are beneficial to all sorts of learners, not just indigenous. In reviewing existing literature, it's been concluded that a Native centered education will reduce unnecessary placement in Special Education. This paper examines why this is so with a specific look at Indigenous students. Through a review of the literature, it's proposed that there are other instructional models to educate these youths so that their needs are met. Successful programs that offer culturally responsive educational programs areas are also looked at as examples to follow for a redesigned educational system.</i></p>
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Introduction

The process of which students are placed in Special Education programs is evolving and has gone through numerous changes by The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) in 2004. (Carter, 2012). This is highly due to the misplacement of marginalized groups into EC services. Native Americans, African Americans, and Hispanic Americans have been placed proportionally more in EC services than other groups, such as Asian American and Caucasian American (Robinson-Zanartu et. Al, 2011). It is important to consider that what constitutes "disabled" in a society can be considered a social construct. (Hausstatter & Connolley, 2012). In American schools, students can be considered disabled if they are unable to succeed in the regular academic setting. However, students who learn differently than the established, the sit and listen learning approaches may get placed into a Special Education program. They may be labeled as having attention deficit disorder and placed as Other Health Impaired or be considered to have a Learning Disability if they struggle with learning Mathematics, Reading or Writing. They could also be considered Emotionally or Behaviorally Disabled if their behavior or emotions interfere with their learning. Behaviors behind these labels may show only in the American traditional academic setting of sitting and listening to direct instructions.

Other learning environments may allow for movement, hands on activities, discussing, interacting with the community, and so forth. In these variable environments, learning difficulties may disappear. In addition, some students with learning disabilities, Autism, or Other Health Impairment do not get the services they need within Special Education. In public schools, the same accommodations, such as extended time on tests, small group setting (where students with different learning needs are placed together, and still do not get individualized instruction), and read aloud on tests, are often applied to students of different categories, such as Other Health Impaired and Learning Disabilities (McCaffrey & Buzick, 2014). The interest of this paper is in determining the experience of Native American students and special education. According to the 2012 US Census Bureau, Native American students are 96% more likely than their non-native peers to be placed in Special Education. Additionally, 79% of these Native American students were classified to have language or speech disabilities. (United States Department of the Interior, 2013). However, studies, such as by Lomawaima & McCarty and Kidman, et. Al. have shown that when native students are offered an education based on their cultural background, including use of language, ritual, and integration with nature, their participation and grades can improve (Lomawaima & McCarty, 2006 and Kidman & Abrams, 2011). Such studies raise the question, if native students are offered culturally appropriate intervention, such as testing in their native language, prior to screening and referral to Special Education Services, could this high incidence of placement decrease? Galla, Kawai'ae'a, & Nicholas write that when students are not offered the education that aligns with their learning styles, they can fall behind in school. Students from different cultural background can be accustomed to learning in a different style and can have trouble adjusting to the traditional Western form of schooling. This paper will examine the criteria that determines placement of a child in Special Education, and the long-term

implications/effects of the process specifically for Indigenous students if cultural factors are not considered. Looking at what specific instructional practices indigenous learners may need in the educational setting through a review of literature that exists on both topics including the existing research on overrepresentation of indigenous students in Special Education settings and comparing the academic achievement of learners when they are provided culturally appropriate learning programs.

Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that given culturally appropriate information structures, fewer of these Indigenous learners will be referred to special education. With a further argument that if students of other marginalized groups receive culturally appropriate instruction, fewer of those students may be referred as well. Regardless of background, if a student is not making academic progress, she/he can be referred to Special Education services. Some of these referrals may be prevented if students receive their education through culturally appropriate instructions. Meaning that indigenous learners may need specific learning instructions based on their cultural and linguistic knowledge and abilities.

Misplacement Evaluation

One of the ways to examine if students are being misplaced and mislabeled is to look at how the regular educational setting is serving the students. Students who are culturally and linguistically diverse, such as indigenous learners are often found to be served disproportionately in Special Education. A 2014 study by Guzman & Fernandez looked at school districts in South Texas and found that there was overrepresentation in multiple categories of Special Education, including Learning Disabled, Emotionally Disturbed, Mental Retarded, and Speech Impairment. They found that many misplacements are due to students underperforming due to language issues, or limited access to standardized education. Students from indigenous backgrounds can experience both. Students of special needs, and students who are indigenous learners may not be appropriately instructed. If it is mostly offered as direct instruction with a set curriculum, it may not be reaching all students. Students who are labeled as Special Needs as well as Gifted may be not receiving the services they need. Students who are of indigenous or marginalized cultural backgrounds may not perform as well as their peers of the dominant cultural groups. When given state exams, scores are often lower for marginalized groups, including, Native American, and students in Special Education (Wright, R., 2009). Studies have shown that indigenous learners can improve test scores if given instruction that is both culturally appropriate and relevant. This includes teaching in the native language, giving hands-on learning opportunities, teaching about the culture, and including the community. A study by McCarty and Lee found that indigenous Navajo students, when offered culturally appropriate education about their culture in their schools, improved academically and surpassed their non-Native peers in many standardized tests (McCarty & Lee, 2014). Another study of Maori students in New Zealand presented the dramatic increase in academic performance and involvement in science once their culture was acknowledged. This included demonstrating that Maoris can have futures in science (Kidman, et. Al., 2010).

Background

The studies mentioned demonstrate that indigenous students are capable of learning school curriculums when provided with culturally appropriate education. With the effects of colonization, schools have skewed mainstream in favor of a Western style education. Shifting it in favor of acknowledging indigenous learners, academic performance can drastically reduce the misplacement of indigenous students in Special Education. Oral tradition, for indigenous cultures, has been a means of preparing youth to succeed within their world. (McCarty & Nicholas, 2014) before the introduction of Western education. When oral tradition was widely used, Native groups had their own tribal language for teaching. When language communicated information, the Native means of viewing and connecting with the world came through. However, when colonists invaded the Americas, and took over the educational system, English was imposed as the language of communication. Native children were forced into Western style schools and made to learn Western language and behavior. The impact of this movement has been traumatic and long lasting. First, generations of Natives began to lose their culture and language. If it was forced out in schools, the children would both naturally lose it from misuse. If forced, they also likely lost the desire to speak it and with time Natives began to take on the thoughts that Westerners put upon them, as being less-than, unable, undesired, and not acceptable... unless they took on Western behaviors. Natives internalized the "less-than" thinking and began to fail at the learning systems put upon them. Not only did they fail in schools, but they also failed in their home and working lives. Many dropped out of school, fell into drugs and alcohol, and lives of poverty. This behavior trickled down to their children, and then, generations of Natives reinforced the thinking amongst themselves of being less capable and valued than their non-Native peers. Therefore, the community became infected with this thinking. Students who were interviewed in a study by Tracy Friedel (2010) about their self-perception stated that they have varied views of themselves as Native learners. They felt hope that they could learn Native culture and feel some value in the community. However,

there was also some doubts felt in their abilities. They had been given feedback from their non-Native peers that they were not expected to succeed at life in the same way as non-Natives. What was strange is that their Native peers also shared the same low expectations. This means that the community of Native Americans were reinforcing amongst themselves that they were less capable than learners of European descent. Learners can have difficulty with finding success if they do not have the motivation to do so. Like with Friedel's study, students who do not believe in their capabilities can lack the motivation to succeed in school. The motivation that students feel can be either intrinsic or extrinsic. If students do not believe in their own abilities, they will not have the intrinsic motivation to do their best. They may not even realize what they are capable of, and believe they are doing their best, because they assume it is the most they can do. Or they may give up, feel frustrated, or disinterested in learning and gaining more knowledge, and just not try because they do not see the point. Often, students are unable to be motivated if their community is unsupportive of their success.

In addition, the feedback of a teacher, peers, school staff, or family can make an impact on a child. If any of these individuals or groups tell a child that they can or cannot perform a function, it may become a self-fulfilling prophecy. The child may be extrinsically unmotivated to function well in school. Therefore, their academic and/or behavioral performance may not be the true representation of how they can truly perform. This will be examined later in this paper. There is a parallel of the limiting perception of learning among Native communities to communities which produce a high percentage of Special Needs learners. These communities may be made up of people who have work options that require only a high school education or less. These work options include farming, industrial factory work, or other hands-on employment (Friedel, 2010). Therefore, education would not have a high priority in the community, and it can trickle down to individual learners. A higher percentage of students from these communities may naturally perform lower in classes and tests, because doing well in school is not as important as learning how to work and have a family. Many Native communities have had work options that include farming as well. Hence, students who could have been exposed to a valuable education in the home, and a supportive attitude in learning, can be discouraged by family and peers to attend post-secondary school. These communities are often middle to working class and have the expectations that children will grow up to gain blue collar jobs (Smyth, 2016). These communities turn out a high percentage of special needs learners. In contrast, communities with higher income earners often expect children to attend college and attain college jobs. These communities have a lower percentage of special needs learners (Blanchett, 2010). What places a child in Special Education? According to the U.S. Department of Education, what starts the process is recommendation for screening by the classroom teacher (U.S. Department of Education, 2010). Students can show behaviors that do not fit the expectations of the mainstream classroom, and the behaviors can match criteria that is required for placement in a category for specialized services. For example, a student who blurts out, moves around during instruction, or confronts peers or the teacher without invitation, all fit the behaviors of students with various disabilities (Emotional, Other Health Impaired, or Learning Disability). However, the student could either feel frustrated, because their style of learning is not being taught, or they could come from a cultural background that is highly interactive (Terry & Irving, 2010). Usually, a child is referred during their elementary years when they first start to show difficulty with reading, writing or math, focus/attention, or behavior. While these difficulties all connect with learning challenges, they could also be due to the student first feeling out of place in the mainstream classroom. Their language, style of learning, or behavior may not be met.

Misplacement Identification

For an indigenous learner, the first step that the teacher takes is to contact the head of the special education department, who will then either perform the work him/herself or select a special education teacher to act as the case manager for that student (even though they are not placed). The selected case manager will contact the parents and request a meeting to discuss the process, and to request written permission to observe the child. This is the first step which involves the family, and this is where the disconnect can start. The special education teacher will then conduct an observation of the classroom, examine grades and student work, and provide the classroom teacher with a feedback form with questions about the students' functioning and academic performance. The answers are marked by bubbling choices, with either yes or no answers, or numerical ratings. The numerical ratings refer to levels of intensity of a demonstrated behavior, such as on a behavior-based assessment. The Conners Rating Scale is an example of an informal assessment for both teachers and parents to complete. It asks for a numerical rating for the intensity of observed behaviors, which can give clues as to whether a child may have a disability. For a child who is experiencing a disconnect with their learning environment, their behaviors may fit a disability, but may not be due to a disability. The teacher may not see this, and they may have an unintended bias as to the intentions behind the behaviors when they report of behaviors and actions on assessments such as this. Additionally, the batteries provide a bias, because they require the actions of a student to be minimized by numerical or yes/no answers. This potential bias serves as an injustice to students of indigenous backgrounds who are not getting their learning needs met in a colonized, mainstreamed classroom setting. After the initial interviews and observations are conducted by teachers, the

special education teacher will process the information by reading the notes, comparing the comments to a baseline of what is considered average performance for a grade level student, and report back to the special education head/chair. The information will be checked for evidence of a potential disability. Examples of evidence include similar scores for undesired classroom behaviors (getting out of seat without permission, blurting out, not completing assignments, not getting on task, etc.) and anecdotal evidence of teachers providing commentary of classroom observations. Student work samples and grades also count as evidence. If there is evidence that an anomaly may be present that fits common behaviors of a child with a disability, then the parents will be contacted again to start the official testing process. If the parents are of a background where they are unable to communicate, feel unable to speak up, or, do not support education, the child's placement (into EC services) can be affected. The child does not get placed if the parent does not want it. Many times, students are initially tested for EC, or placed because the parents go with the teachers and school's recommendation. The parents may feel that their opinion does not count, they don't understand, or they do not care. This is where a child can be unfairly placed (Terry & Irving, 2010). A child can be placed based on their scores on testing, or their behavior in school. The behavior can relate to frustration, feeling out of place, needing attention, or not understanding. It may not necessarily be due to a disability with attention or with emotions/behaviors. A child who is indigenous and feeling lost, less able, or less important than their non-indigenous peers can show their frustration through their behavior. If they are placed in EC because of behavior, it can continue the actions by the school of saying they are less than their peers. EC placement can say to a child or their family that they are less able to succeed. Indigenous families can get this feedback already by non-natives within their community. A legal placement in EC can just expand this feeling and treatment. If a student comes from a cultural background which is unique to a school, their methods of communication and learning may not be understood. For example, a study of Tewa Native American children by Costa-Guerra, & Costa-Guerra (2016), showed that their use of vocabulary was unique. Specific objects and items are referred to with non-specific vocabulary, such as "this", or "stuff". To those who do not understand the Tewa language use, it can seem like their language (written and reading) can lag behind non-Tewa and appear as a learning disability. There was a higher percentage of placement among the Tewa Indians in comparison to non-native learners. The researchers examined why this was so, and they learned that culturally, Tewa tend to not be as outspoken. This can be interpreted as having a language deficit. There have been multiple studies of African American students being overrepresented in Special Education, due to the opposite reason (Artiles & Trent, 1994, Smyth, 2016, and Terry & Irving, 2010). This student body can express language verbally and non-verbally in a different style than their peers, and be referred for Special Education for behavior, focus, or academic performance. These are just two examples of what can happen during the overall Special Education referral process. Placing a child in a Special Education program can affect the child's self-esteem. Students are treated differently than their peers by being placed in a separate setting, or, in a general education class with an additional inclusion teacher. Peers can notice the separation because the student will go to different classrooms and must attend IEP meetings (if in high school or older). It will become clear that the student who is placed in Special Education does not learn nor perform as well as others. Because school encompasses so much of a child's day, the length of time spent being made to feel inferior to others due to learning abilities can affect self-esteem. Students in Special Education can struggle with this. Students who come from marginalized groups, such as indigenous learners, can really struggle with this if placed in Special Education. Indigenous cultures have struggled enough with the aftereffects of colonization, including, being made to feel less capable or valued. Placing children needlessly in Special Education is just another attack on the culture. It must stop.

Methods

An Overview of Successful Programs

Schools that have offered education to students that tailor to their culture has seen an increase in academic and functioning performance. This imposes questions regarding the schools' function and methods for implementing such educational techniques into regular school settings. If all-inclusive Native schools show improvement in the academic and functional abilities of the children, might the techniques have similar positive benefits and outcomes for all students? How could such additional techniques be offered in the schools? Who would offer the specialized services, and how would they be performed in the school setting? There will be provided a brief overview of the all-inclusive Native schools to show examples of how they have benefitted students, as well as examine schools which offer some culturally sensitive instruction, results comparison, and finally a discussion of the practicalities of offering such a solution.

Results and Discussion

Successful Programs

There have been studies of schools which offer both full Native American cultural education, and partial cultural education. A cultural education offers classes about the history of the culture, teaches the meaning of rituals and practices, offers instruction of the language and often in the language providing instruction on culturally

appropriate ways. For example, a study by Kidman (2011) compares how science is taught in Maori schools versus Mopan schools. Due to science being taught in accordance with a set curriculum and is presented as a field for which older white (Western) males to pursue as a career, the Maori children are not interested, because they do not find it relevant to them and their futures. In contrast, the Mopan students have higher interest in science, when the schools try to incorporate their culture into the curriculum and give them motivation to pursue science. This is accomplished by exposing the children to scientists who are Mopan, to teach students that there is a possible future for them in the study. Giving students a reason why their education is significant is one huge factor in motivating them to learn. The Mopan, in bringing Mopan scientists to schools, demonstrated to the students that they, being Mopan, can succeed just as well as non-Mopan students. In contrast, the Maori students felt that science was too lofty of a field for them, because of their belief that their ethnicity made them incapable, and that science did not belong to them. Another study by Smyth (2016), discusses how students of underrepresented backgrounds often internalize the assumptions made by dominant groups and then perform in accordance to what is expected by these groups. A study on how Dine students learn in school proposed a way in which indigenous learners could be served in an academic setting. Dine students learn through observation, listening, experiencing, and being taught through stories and metaphors (Cajete, G., 2014). Additionally, Lomawaima (2006) points out that Native learners benefit from having a strong sense of self and identity and knowing where they came from. They need a high connection to their community. When their ancestors were forced into boarding schools to learn a Western style of education and behavior, they had to adapt to established social hierarchies. One established hierarchy was that Westerners were considered civilized and intelligent, and they were seen as savages, or noble savages at best. Lomawaima argues that the adaptation into fitting the mold of Western expectations became internalized into the mindset of many Native American communities. They became disconnected from their communities and lost their sense of self and identity. Native groups, like the Dine, need to regain their identity in the schools by being instructed in ways that are culturally and linguistically appropriate. Since students spend so much of their days at school, the environment can overwhelm students who do not fit in. Native American students, whose culture is based on involvement with the community, family, work, and nature, are encouraged by schools to let that go in place of competing with peers. Schools do not have a means of teaching students to celebrate their identities and heritage, nor connect with their community. It is all about testing (Terry & Irving, 2010). They are also encouraged to drop their heritage in favor of following the culture of the school. Schools, being Western in teaching and learning styles, push for a culture that does not fit the Native standard. Instead of being connected to others, it praises disconnect. Students who underperform in schools may either have a natural learning disability, may not be able to learn in the style offered in the classroom, or may lack the motivation and drive to achieve. Friedel (2010) found that many First Nation youth, when interviewed, felt that society expected them to live working-class to poor lifestyle, and pursue a hopeless future of drugs and alcohol. That sort of pressure is damaging to the self-esteem of an individual. What would be the point of achieving in school if one is expected to not amount to much? In contrast, exposing underrepresented youth to successful people of their culture can be an inspiration and motivator for students to perform better in school. How could public schools manage community outreach as a means of intervention for struggling learners? While some schools offer assemblies for students to meet successful people in the community and outward, more could be done. There could be opportunities for volunteers from the underrepresented communities to visit and help the students, which would inspire and encourage the students. People from the same communities who have been successful can visit and interact with the students, like the Mopan scientists visited the Mopan students and encouraged them to get interested in science.

Program Evaluation

Perhaps this simple intervention of introducing successful people to students would encourage them to perform better in schools and avoid being misplaced in Special Education services. Including heritage and culture back into schools helped students to such an extreme, that their standardized testing scores elevated considerably (Costa-Guerra, et. Al., 2016). This proves that Native students, when given the chance, can be just as capable, if not more so, as their non-Native peers. In fact, not only would fewer students of indigenous backgrounds get placed in Special Education, but potentially, a smaller percentage of the group in comparison to non-Native peers. Possibly, if all students of all backgrounds had their culture acknowledged and respected, their learning would improve, their scores would increase, and fewer would be referred to Special Education. Some schools, especially high schools, require students to have a senior project in order to graduate. In addition, schools will require students to give back to the community for a set number of hours in order to earn required credits to graduate. For example, the Vail School District, in Tucson, Arizona, requires all high school seniors to complete a project. The senior project states that students must research an area of interest, participate with a community to get the results that they need, and present their results to a school community. The other project, requiring giving back to the community, includes volunteering and creating solutions (such as building park benches) to help people. Students, such as Native Americans, who are already involved with their community, can get credit and encouragement to do the actions and behaviors of which they are accustomed to. They can

pursue what they have been raised to believe is of value. This action of schools is a strong start towards re-creating a sense of identity and connectiveness to the community. It also helps students step outside of the role of being competitive individuals and helping give back.

Conclusion

The studies mentioned demonstrate a step towards community involvement, aiming to encourage students to practice their language and communication skills. In addition, students who struggle behaviorally also can improve, because they must get outside of themselves in order to reach out to others. Studies have also shown that volunteering has been helpful to students with behavioral problems (Billig, 2000). The steps that schools are taking with high school students are a good way to provide intervention with students who have special needs in behavior, attention, and learning disabilities in reading and writing. The senior projects which require communication, research, and creating a final paper can be just that push to motivate students to overcome challenges with learning disabilities. However, schools should also do more for students who are at the elementary age. This can provide an intervention for students who are referred with learning disabilities, attention difficulties, and behavioral problems. The schools which are all Native American inclusive, introduce community involvement at a very young age. Also proposed was the addition of a culturally sensitive staff member, such as a person who serves students of cultural backgrounds and differences (Robinson-Zanartu, et. Al., 2011). An English as a Second Language (ESL) teacher helps students with language, the same could be for a cultural teacher helping students with culture. The ESL teaching program requires students to learn communication, writing, and vocabulary, and the students apply their knowledge towards real life situations (U.S. Department of Education, 2017). The cultural teaching program could have a set of criteria which teaches about the students' native cultures and of other cultures served in the school, and apply the knowledge to research, action, and participation. This could help students with feeling a better sense of self-worth, because their identities are respected and appreciated, and then, they could feel more encouraged to participate in school. In addition, including the community to students at a young age can also be helpful. In reviewing existing literature, I have concluded that a Native centered education will reduce unnecessary placement in Special Education. Studies have demonstrated that if students are encouraged by successful people of their heritage, they will drastically improve academically. This can be accomplished in a multitude of ways some involve having professionals such as the scientists of the Mopan community visit is an example of inspiring students to engage in science. Hiring and supporting teachers of the same or similar indigenous backgrounds. Acknowledging the language needs of students such as offering instruction in the native tongue can reduce some learning challenges that can show up as a reading or writing disability (or create behavioral or attention problems).

Improving community involvement, such as bringing in volunteers from families of the underrepresented students, having teacher outreach (in visiting homes and rituals), and encouraging practice of instruction at home can all play a factor in increasing the performance of a child in school. Insights from this literature review will assist special education educators a well-rounded perspective on the students they may encounter as future teachers of Special Education. Providing awareness on issues of misplacement and misrepresentation of cultural and linguistic minorities in Special Education, and in addition, provide literature on the different learning styles of ethnic groups.

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